

The engagement of students using the virtual platform tools. A successful case in a required subject of 1st year in mathematics in engineering (UPC)

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ABSTRACT

Fonaments matemàtics is a required 1st year subject in engineering career at the university EPSEVG (*Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya*) with approximately 270 students enrolled each semestre that traditionally it had a medium pass rate.

Over the last 6 years we have introduced gradual changes in the teaching planning of it with the idea of achieving: 1) that students work throughout the course, 2) leveling knowledge and 3) reduce the number of students not presented to any exam. The changes have been implemented and corrected based on our feedback from students (engagement, grades, acceptance and survey assessments). The introduction of the calculator, laptops and tablets in everyday life and the use of the tools of the UPC virtual platform have been key.

In this contribution, we present the strategies used and the good results obtained.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) is a federated university that brings together 16 school centres, such as the *Escola Politècnica Superior d'Enginyeria de Vilanova i la Geltrú* (EPSEVG) [1]. EPSEVG is a School Engineering centre since 1901, currently with 6 Bachelor's degrees in industrial and ICT engineering and about 1400 students. The paper focus on the analysis of a required subject of 1st semester (1st year) at the EPSEVG, called *Fonaments matemàtics* (hereafter FOMA) with about 260 students enrolled each year (in Setember). Specifically the study is done with the students of Bachelor's degree in: Industrial Design and Product Development Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Industrial Electronics and Automatic Control Engineering, Electrical Engineering and Marine Sciences and Technologies. All students of different degrees are mixed and divided into 5 groups of about 52 students each group and the teaching involves between 3 and 5 teachers.

The type of student enrolled in this subject is heterogeneous in terms of knowledge of mathematics and in general with low cut-off marks. For example, in the academic year 2020-21, 1st semester of which the school already has a published report (see Table 1), 246 students were enrolled, the cut-off mark for entering university (moving in the interval [5,14]) was 5.4, ie the student's grade with the worst grade), of which 58% have a low grade, in the range [5,8) with respect to previous studies before university. In addition, the type of student is heterogeneous with respect to the knowledge of mathematics acquired: 17% of students come from 'higher degree training courses' (CFGS) and therefore have a very low level of mathematics while the remaining 83% have entered through the PAU tests. The university entrance exam (PAU) is a requirement for students with a high school diploma or equivalent to enter college. In summary, traditionally FOMA had a low-medium pass rate (see Table 1).

Table 1. Enrolled students at FOMA subject (EPSEVG) each semester since 6 years ago and cut-off mark for entering EPSEVG.

Semester	Enrolled	Cut-off mark
	#	[5-14]
2016-17Q1	277	5,34
2017-18Q1	247	5
2018-19Q1	259	5,25
2019-20Q1	273	5,3
2020-21Q1	246	5,4
2021-22Q1	276	5,94

1.2 Contents and teaching planning

FOMA gives the student the first mathematical contents at the university: 1) calculus of one variable like differential and basic integral calculus, 2) linear algebra with linear systems, vectorial spaces and basic linear applications (with only diagonal matrix associated).

The distribution of classes throughout the course is: 2 sessions of 2 hours per week during the 15 weeks of the course. Although the Bologna plans are being implemented, and all subjects should be assessed continuously throughout the course, in practice it is very common for subjects to be assessed with only two exams: a mid-term partial examination and a final exam at the end of the course, proof of this is that EPSEVG has reserved two weeks exclusively for the partial and final exams, respectively.

In this article, when we refer to continuous assessment, we mean all the acts we do throughout the course, in addition to the partial and final exams.

The coordinator of FOMA for 6 years, since 2016-17 academic year, in its beginning focused on placing teaching in the context of engineering adding to the traditional CV the learning of errors and numerical methods, as well as the use of calculators and the computer in the day to day - with the use of Matlab / Octave or Geogebra software - as complementary work tools.

Over the years, there have been several mathematics teachers who have helped at some point in this process of change - all of them highly qualified with a teaching career of no less than 20 years.

During the covid-19 period the teaching was completely online and we designed Moodle activities for the students. In the last two years, we have taken advantage of it and increased the online activities of the continuous assessment.

In this paper we show the academic planning of FOMA and the academic results.

2 METHODOLOGY

To compensate for the lack of homogeneity in mathematical knowledge and in general the low rate of the students (see section 1.2), the teachers involved continuously try different strategies. In general teachers try

- to avoid bad academic results,
- to reduce the number of students not presented to any exam,
- to promote that students work throughout the course,
- to level mathematical knowledge.

Specifically over the last 6 years we have introduced gradual changes in the teaching planning of it with the idea of achieving it.

The changes have been implemented and corrected based on our feedback from students (engagement, grades, acceptance and survey assessments). The introduction of the calculator, laptops and tablets in everyday life and the use of the (Moodle) tools of the UPC virtual platform have been key.

2.1 Continuous evaluable activity

Table 2 shows, across the years, the evolution of the design of the continuous evaluable activity, number of activities and weight.

The table does not show the self-learning activities in the virtual classroom that were prepared from the beginning so that they would be leveled in Derivatives and Integrals, these activities were very well received and are introduced in all courses somehow. These are Moodle quizzes with Wiris [4] which can be done as many times as you want, and the solution always comes out. Wiris math calculator is integrated in the UPC Moodle platform and allows you to define quizzes with random parameters / constants, and mathematical tools. This is the strategy we propose to level knowledge.

Table 2. Design of the continuous evaluable activity at FOMA subject (EPSEVG) each semester during 6 years.

Semester	Weight	Hand exercises per student		Moodle activity per student		PC activities per student	
		%	#	%	#	%	#
2016-17Q1	25	-	-	-	-	25	2
2017-18Q1	40	-	-	-	-	40	2
2018-19Q1	40	-	-	-	-	40	2
2019-20Q1	40	-	-	5	1	35	2
2020-21Q1	50	-	-	10	2	30	2
2021-22Q1	40	5	2	20	10	15	1

Table Moodle activities are Wiris-type quizzes where questions are taken at random from a question bag. The questionnaires are individual, lasting 1h, distributed throughout the course to do at home, from Friday to Monday, with between 3 and 5 attempts, each time a quizze of the same type but different questions. The grade obtained is the maximum of the attempts grades. We propose this strategy to make the student work continuously and do not leave the subject.

The PC activities consists of doing an individualized project at home during 5 days, in pairs or individually, with the computer and the use of Matlab / Octave and Geogebra. This is performed in order to develop the students skills in applied mathematics and allow the mobile / tablets, calculators or laptop to form part of the learning process of the subject and not just tools for personal use. The hand exercises are individual, performed in class, previously notified, with notes and calculator and under the supervision of the teacher. The aim is to prepare for specific problems of interest to the subject that may arise in the exams. Finally, all these strategies were implemented together in the continued activity of last semester 2021-22.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Continued academic results

We find the relevant academic results during last semester 2021-22, and that can be compared somehow to 2019-20 one, when begun the use of the Moodle tools of the Virtual Platform, in form of quizzes (see Table 3). The more deliverables you order, the more they make. Especially important is that when we increase the number of quizzes, and therefore make them follow in time, the percentage of students who do not do any activity drops from 9 to 3. And total deliveries move to 668 to 6657. Also relevant that deliveries per enrolled student increase from 2.6 to 25. Last setember, an student that followed the course sent an average of 29 activities.

Table 3. Continued academic results and survey satisfaction at FOMA subject (EPSEVG) each semester during last 2 years, except the covid-19 semester.

Semester	Total deliveries	Deriveries per student rated	Deliveries per student	Students without any delivery
	#	#	#	%
2019-20Q1	698	2,81	2,56	9,2
2021-22Q1	6657	28,8	25,0	2,9

3.2 Continued academic results of 2021-22Q1 semester

The engagement of 276 students is shown in figures 1 where for each activity (quizzes) it is plotted: the number of deliveries (between 3 to 5 attempts of each quiz), the averaged grade (the grade is the maximum of all attempt) and the percentage of students that deliver it. Last deliver (no 10) was two days before Christmas.

Figure 1. Continued assessment results in 2021-22Q1 semester for each (approximately) weekly deliver at the x axis (time line).

3.3 Academic results

The objective data for measuring the results can be found in Table 4. Table shows information of final grades of students every semester since 6 years ago,:

- the average final grade (measured from 0 to 10), calculated with respect all enrolled students,
- the percentage of not presented students to any evaluative act, the approved students with a grade greater or equal 5 and finally the excellent grades.

Table 4. Global academic results and survey satisfaction at FOMA subject (EPSEVG) each semester during 6 years. NP=not presented, A=Aproved (≥ 5), E=Excellent (≥ 9)

Semester	Average grade (0-10)	NP %	A %	E %	Student survey %	Rating survey (1-5)
2016-17Q1	4.6	10,11	54,2	6,86	27	3,8
2017-18Q1	3.8	7,69	44,9	1,62	37	3,1
2018-19Q1	4,6	9,30	55,2	1,50	27	3,2
2019-20Q1	4,6	6,96	61,17	0,73	24	3,1
2020-21Q1	-	5,28	82,93	13,82	-	-
2021-22Q1	5	4,70	59,00	2,50	11	4,2

Firstly observe that the grades of covid-19 period (2020-21Q1) are out of context, as the teaching was completely online and all the evaluative acts were performed at home, with quizzes and without any physical control of teachers. Eventhough the

grades are overdimensioned, a value to keep in mind is the small value of 5.3% of not presented students, compared with the 10% we had at 2016-17. At that time the students were confined at home every day; that value probably approaches the minimum possible of non presented. It is gratifying to see that we have even improved this value in the last semester to a 4.7% of non presented.

We also observe that the total average grade increases to 5 at last semester, and we reach a 59% of approved with 2.5% of excellent results. Although it has been passed with higher average grade, in return it has been more difficult for students to obtain maximum marks, above 9.5.

Table 4 also shows the survey results from students:

- Percentage student that perform the survey.
- Rating survey, from 1 to 5, agreement to the question: 'Overall I am satisfied with this subject'. In the context of the EPSEVG school, the answer of this question is 3.6 in mean value of all subjects.

Again last semester, FOMA has the best ratings, compared with other semesters, improving the average school result. It is right that there is a low percentage of students who take the survey, but experience tells us that when there are few students who take the survey, they are the ones who are dissatisfied with the subject.

The personal perception and the feedback received from the students and comments to the surveys tell us that they don't like, or find it difficult, to run the Matlab / Octave programs, anyway they still gain skills in their applied use, as we have seen when students have to use it in other subjects of higher semesters.

The other perception of all the teachers of the subject is regarding the last semester, taken from the comments of the students in class, in all the groups, it is that: it has gone very well and the students liked to have the questionnaires every weekend for practice, even stated this in the survey comments.

Finally, the downside is that it has taken a lot of work for the teachers involved to prepare the material and follow up, that includes preparing and activating quizzes, correcting problems, projects and exams.

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